

ILOILO SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY SECURITY MANAGEMENT CAPABILITY: BASIS FOR FORMULATING SECURITY MANAGEMENT ACTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study attempted to determine the security management capability of Iloilo Science Technology University-Miagao Campus in terms of Physical Security Management and Risk and Security Hazard Analysis Management as assessed by the students, faculty members and non-teaching personnel. This descriptive study used a survey questionnaire in gathering data. Data were statistically treated using frequency count, percentage, mean and rank. The finding as to the Physical Security Management capacity is satisfactory as assessed by the students and non-teaching personnel. On the other hand, faculty members claimed that it is very satisfactory. The same data revealed that Risk and Security Hazard Analysis Management capability of ISAT U Miagao Campus is satisfactory. Aside from determining the Physical Security Management and Risk and Security Hazard Analysis Management capabilities, respondents also gave suggestions on how to improve in general the Security Management of ISAT U Miagao Campus. The top three suggestions of the students as identified by them were increasing the number of security personnel, providing, upgrading, and modernizing security equipment and conducting regular seminar-orientation on the security manual particularly on the code of conduct and work ethics of the security profession. When the faculty members were asked to offer their suggestions on how to improve the security management of ISAT U Miagao Campus, respondents said that seminar-orientation on the security manual particularly on the code of conduct and work ethics of the security profession should be conducted regularly. Respondents also proposed that the ISAT University Security Manual to be used as a guiding principle of the security office should be enhanced and strengthened. When the opinion of the non-teaching personnel was solicited, providing, upgrading, and modernizing security equipment emerged as the number one recommendation.

Keywords: Security management, physical security management, risk and security hazard analysis management

Introduction

Background of the Study

Violence in schools creates a climate of anxiety and fear, which weakens the core educational purpose which is to provide quality education for all in a health and safe environment. Security is one of the prime concerns of Iloilo Science and Technology University as it is considered as one of the important components of student services. However, for several years that ISAT U Miagao Campus has been implementing its security measures, no good track record in doing it has been established as well as no formal and clear assessment, evaluation and reports has been made to determine its effects on the students and employees.

In addition, no studies have been conducted as to what other aspects and areas of the security management program needs to be improved and to come up with an action plan for a much better delivery of the said program.

In line with this premise, the researchers find a necessity to study, investigate, analyze and give possible suggestions on how to improve in particular the security management of ISAT U Miagao Campus.

Research Questions

ISAT U Miagao Campus has been implementing its security management for the past several years. Sound management would call for a review of the program and its execution in the light of looking into its relevance, adequacy and implications on students, faculty members and non-teaching personnel.

For better understanding of the study, the following queries were raised:

1. What is the security management capability of Iloilo Science and Technology University Miagao Campus as assessed by the students, faculty members and non-teaching personnel in terms of:
 - a. Physical Security Management
 - b. Risk and Security Hazard Analysis Management
2. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan can be proposed to further improve the security management capability of Iloilo Science and Technology University Miagao Campus?

Theoretical Framework

The success or effectiveness of security management depends largely on the availability and adequate appropriations of both human and non-human resources as well as the capacity to hurdle the odds or hindrances that affect the programs.

In line with this, one basic theory that can be applied in this study is the system approach theory. According to this theory, a system is a set of interrelated parts that function as a whole to achieve a common purpose, it functions by acquiring inputs from the external environment, transforming them in some ways, and discharging outputs back to the environment (Daft, 2005).

Conceptual Framework

This study aimed to fully identify the security management capability of ISAT U Miagao Campus in terms of Physical Security Management and Risk and Security Hazard Analysis Management

The overall framework to guide the analysis of the study is presented in a system model (Figure 1). The schematic diagram consists of three major variables: input, process and output. Consistent with the systems thinking, the inputs are transformed into outputs through

conversion processes taking place. The input consists of the existing security management of ISAT U Miagao Campus, while the assessment of Physical Security Management and Risk and Security Hazard Analysis Management becomes the process or conversion sub-system. The output variable points to the formulation of Security Management Action Plan.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Figure1. The Paradigm of the Study

Method

Instrumentation and Data Collection

This study was conducted at the Iloilo Science and Technology University Miagao Campus. This study used the descriptive-analytical research technique that identifies, describes and analyzes the security management of ISAT U Miagao Campus in terms of physical security management and risk and security hazard analysis management. The respondents comprised of ISAT U Miagao Campus students, faculty members and non-teaching personnel whose numbers were determined through convenience sampling. This was used because of the respondents' convenient accessibility and proximity to the researchers. A total of 54 students, 18 faculty members and 11 non-teaching personnel participated in the study. A survey questionnaire was the main instrument in gathering the data. The questionnaire that determined the physical security management was taken from the security manual of ISAT U while questions on the risk and security hazard analysis management were patterned after the study of Presado. Data were statistically treated using frequency count, percentage, mean and rank.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Students	54	65.0
Faculty	18	21.7
Non-teaching Personnel	11	13.3
Total	83	100

Results and Discussion

On Physical Security Management Capacity

The finding as to the physical security management capacity of ISAT UMiagao Campus is satisfactory as assessed by the students and non-teaching personnel with mean of 2.64 and 3.42 respectively. On the other hand, faculty members claimed that is very satisfactory with mean of 3.69. This result clearly signifies that the Physical Security Management capacity of ISAT UMiagao Campus is acceptable, though not excellent. This further indicates that the security personnel's capacity in terms of enforcing rules, regulations and policies of the university as well as prioritizing the safety and security of personnel, students and properties of the university is not adequate and needs to be enhanced.

Table 2: Physical Security Management Capacity

Respondents	Mean	Description
Students	2.64	Satisfactory
Faculty Members	3.69	Very Satisfactory
Non-teaching Personnel	3.42	Satisfactory

On Risk and Security Hazard Analysis Management Capacity

The data revealed that Risk and Security Hazard Analysis management capacity of ISAT U Miagao Campus is satisfactory as assessed by students with mean of 2.75, faculty members with mean of 3.40 and non-teaching personnel with 3.47. This findings show that the security personnel's capacity is acceptable, although there are aspects and areas that need to be improved in terms of conducting risk and security analysis, implementing rules, regulations and policies to ensure preventive measures for possible threats, risk and hazards, cooperating with all the people in the university to ensure smooth evaluation of potential risk and hazard and in submitting accurate and reliable reports to the security office and school administration for proper address of the issue on the risk and hazard in the university.

Table 3: Risk and Security Hazard Analysis Management Capacity

Respondents	Mean	Description
Students	2.75	Satisfactory
Faculty Members	3.40	Satisfactory
Non-teaching Personnel	3.47	Satisfactory

Suggestions on How to Improve the Security Management of ISAT University Miagao Campus by Students

Aside from determining the Physical Security Management Capacity and Risk and Security Hazard Analysis Management Capacity, respondents also gave suggestions on how to improve in general the Security Management of ISAT University Miagao Campus. Table 4 presents the result of the survey for the students. The top three suggestions of the students as identified by them were increasing the number of security personnel, providing, upgrading, and modernizing security equipment and conducting regular seminar-orientation on the security manual particularly on the code of conduct and work ethics of the security profession.

Data suggests that students feel more secured with the presence of more security personnel as this will help reduce violence inside the campus. Having enough number of security personnel in the university can produce positive results because they can provide not only security but also guidance for students. ISAT U Miagao Campus has a lot of entrances and exits and involved hundreds or more people coming and going out daily. Therefore, it's imperative to have increased security personnel to check on students, employees, outsiders and school properties.

Table 4: Suggestions on How to Improve the Security Management of ISAT U Miagao Campus

<i>Suggestions</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Increasing the number of security personnel	46	1
Upgrading, and modernizing security equipment	42	2
Enhancing and strengthening of the ISAT U security manual to be used as guiding principle of the security office	37	3
Regular conduct of seminar-orientation on the security manual particularly on the code of conduct and work ethics of the security profession	35	4
Safety and security planning operations		
Imposition of sanctions or disciplinary actions on violative/erring security personnel	29	5.5
Pre-employment screening/training of the members of the security personnel	29	5.5
Holding regular meetings for the members of the security personnel	27	7
Physical security review	25	8
Hazard analysis	12	9
Safety and security policy review	10	10

By Faculty Members

When the faculty members were asked to offer their suggestions on how to improve the security management of ISAT U Miagao Campus, 17 out of 18 respondents as illustrated in table 5 said that seminar-orientation on the security manual particularly on the code of conduct and work ethics of the security profession should be conducted regularly. Same number of respondents also proposed that the ISAT University Security Manual to be used as guiding principle of the security office should be enhanced and strengthened.

This finding proposes that any organization including ISAT U Miagao Campus must plan and allocate adequate time and resources towards security personnel seminar-orientation on the code of conduct and work ethics in order to equip security personnel with knowledge and skills that will help them to tackle ethical dilemmas among other ethical challenges inherent in the workplace.

Equally important is the enhancement and strengthening of the institution of its Security Manual. Campus security and safety is an important feature of ISAT U brand of education. This academic institution is highly committed to providing students with a much safer learning environment. These goals can only be advanced by revisiting the university's Security Manual. ISAT U can't become stagnant with its safety and security policies because there are always new challenges that need to be addressed.

Table 5: Suggestions on How to Improve the Security Management of ISAT U Miagao Campus

Suggestions	Frequency Count	Rank
Regular conduct of seminar-orientation on the security manual particularly on the code of conduct and work ethics of the security profession	17	1.5
Enhancing and strengthening the ISAT U security manual to be used as Guiding principle of the security office	17	1.5
Increasing the number of security personnel	16	3
Upgrading, and modernizing security equipment	15	4
Pre-employment screening/training of the members of the security personnel	14	5
Safety and security planning operations	10	6.5
Safety and security policy review	10	6.5
Hazard analysis	10	6.5
Holding regular meetings for the members of the security personnel	8	9
Imposition of sanctions or disciplinary actions on violative/erring security personnel	6	10

By Non-teaching Personnel

When the opinion of the non-teaching personnel were solicited on how to improve the security management of ISAT U Miagao Campus, table 6 shows that providing, upgrading, and modernizing security equipment emerged as the number one recommendation. This suggests that ISAT University must promote a safe learning environment where students can grow, thrive, and prepare for a lifetime of achievement by investing on the upgrading and modernization of its security equipment. Improving the quality of security equipment is an expensive undertaking. However, the positive impacts of such modernization on students and employees will outstrip the cost of the investment.

Table 6: Suggestions on How to Improve the Security Management of ISAT U Miagao Campus

Suggestions	Frequency Count	Rank
Upgrading, and modernizing security equipment	11	1
Increasing the number of security personnel	10	2.5
Regular conduct of seminar-orientation on the security manual particularly on the code of conduct and work ethics of the security profession	10	2.5
Safety and security planning operations	10	2.5
Holding regular meetings for the members of the security personnel	10	2.5
Enhancing and strengthening of the ISAT U security manual to be used as Guiding principle of the security office	10	2.5
Pre-employment screening/training of the members of the security personnel	8	7
Imposition of sanctions or disciplinary actions on violative/erring security personnel	7	8.5
Hazard analysis	7	8.5
Safety and security policy review	6	10

Conclusion

The result clearly signifies that the Physical Security Management capability of ISAT University Miagao Campus is acceptable, though not excellent. This further indicates that the security personnel's capability in terms of enforcing rules, regulations and policies of the university as well as prioritizing the safety and security of personnel, students and properties of the university is not adequate and needs to be enhanced.

Another finding shows that the Risk and Security Hazard Analysis Management capability is acceptable, although there are aspects and areas that need to be revisited and improved such as the conduct of risk and security hazard analysis, evaluation of potential risk and hazard inside the campus and develop a system or mechanism of reporting by the security personnel and school administrators to address the issue on the risk and hazard in the university.

Recommendations

Strategies on how to improve the Physical Security Management such as increasing the number of security personnel, upgrading, and modernizing security equipment, and enhancing and strengthening of the ISAT University Security Manual should be included in the formulation of ISAT University Miagao Campus Security Management Action Plan.

Policies on how to improve the Risk and Security Hazard Analysis Management such as review of safety and security policy and assessment of safety and security planning operations should also be included in the formulation of ISAT University Miagao Campus Security Management Action Plan.

Based on shared suggestions and recommendations by the respondents, this Security Management Action Plan for ISAT U Miagao Campus was formulated.

Iloilo Science and Technology University – Miagao Campus Security Management Action Plan (A.Y. 2020-2021)

Strategic Action Description	Person/Office Responsible	Date to Begin	Date Due	Resources Required	Potential Problem/Hazard	Desired Outcome
Increase of the number of security personnel which can be patterned on ratio between the security personnel and the population of the university	Office of the Campus Administrator Human Resource Department Accounting Office Office of Safety, Security, Environment and Disaster Mitigation Management Security Officer	January, 2021	January, 2022	Money Manpower	Insufficient funds Staffing requirements are not fully understood	Increased in the number of Security Personnel to enforce security rules, regulations and policies of the university
Regular conduct of seminar-orientation on the security manual particularly on the code of conduct and work ethics of the security profession	Office of the Campus Administrator Office of Safety, Security, Environment and Disaster Mitigation Management Guidance and Counselling Office Private Individual/ Security Agency Security Officer	June, 2021	July, 2021	Money Manpower Method	Insufficient funds ISAT University Security Manual is poorly designed and structured Lack of competent professional and technical know-how	Seminar-Orientation on the code of conduct and work ethics of security profession will be adopted as an annual activity of the University
Purchase, upgrading, and modernizing of security equipment	Office of the Campus Administrator Finance Office Office of Safety, Security, Environment and Disaster Mitigation Management Security Officer	January, 2021	January, 2022	Money Method	Insufficient funds Bureaucratic delays Procurement knowledge and expertise at policy and operational levels are inadequate	Availability of upgraded and modernized security equipment
Enhance and strengthen the ISAT U Security Manual to be used as guiding principle of the security office	Office of Safety, Security, Environment and Disaster Mitigation Management Security Officer	June, 2021	July, 2021	Money Manpower Method Material	Non-Existence or Out-dated Security Manual Lack of competent professional and technical know-how in designing security manual Security Manual is built behind closed doors Failure to communicate properly the Security Manual especially to the security personnel	An Enhanced and Strengthened ISAT University Miagao Campus Security Manual
Safety planning operations	Office of the Campus Administrator Office of Safety, Security, Environment and Disaster Mitigation Management	January, 2021	January, 2022	Financial Manpower Method Materials	Insufficient funds Absence of consistent methodology for planning and executing projects Weak leadership Poor communication and coordination	Implementation of safety planning operations

References

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